

Master's thesis on Sound and Music Computing
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SATB Voice Segregation For Monoaural Recordings

Darius Arthur Pétermann

Supervisors: Pritish Chandna and Jordi Bonada

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Dedication

I dedicate this work to everyone I've crossed path with through my journey as a musician and engineer, to the ones who helped, guided, and inspired me. From my early years as a drum student and drum teacher, to my mentor, teacher, and friend Al Widmoser, to my undergraduate years at the *Berklee College of Music*, to my teacher and mentor Dr. Richard Boulanger. I'd like to also dedicate this work to our small and intimate community of engineers and scientists, all working towards our common goal of sound and music understanding. Lastly, I'd like to dedicate this work to my family, for their unconditional love and support.

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Abstract

Choral singing is a widely practiced form of ensemble singing wherein a group of people sing simultaneously in polyphonic harmony. The most commonly practiced setting for choir ensembles consists of four parts; Soprano, Alto, Tenor and Bass (SATB), each with its own range of fundamental frequencies (F0s). The task of source separation for this choral setting entails separating the SATB mixture into its constituent parts. Source separation for musical mixtures is well studied and many Deep Learning-based methodologies have been proposed for the same. However, most of the research has been focused on a typical case which consists in separating vocal, percussion and bass sources from a mixture, each of which has a distinct spectral structure. In contrast, the simultaneous and harmonic nature of ensemble singing leads to high structural similarity and overlap between the spectral components of the sources in a choral mixture, making source separation for choirs a harder task than the typical case. This, along with the lack of an appropriate consolidated dataset has led to a dearth of research in the field so far. In this work we first assess how well some of the recently developed methodologies for musical source separation perform for the case of SATB choirs. We then propose a novel domain-specific adaptation for conditioning the recently proposed U-Net architecture for musical source separation using the fundamental frequency contour of each of the singing groups and demonstrate that our proposed approach surpasses results from domain-agnostic architectures. Lastly we assess our approach using different evaluation methodologies, going from objective to subjective-based ones, and provide a comparative analysis of the various results.

Keywords: source separation, singing voice, SATB recording, convolutional neural networks, choir music.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Source separation, a task which consists in separating a given mixed signal into its various constitutive components, has long been studied across many different fields; from stock market predictions, to text document analysis and geological predictions among others, source separation finds its level of application. In the case involving musical signals, the task entails separating a given audio mixture into its individual instruments. For a long time now, audio researchers have been using methods centered around classical signal processing: methods such as principal component analysis (PCA) or Non-negative matrix factorization (NMF), although proving to be fairly effective, were hand-crafted and tuned to a small number of data.

In recent years, deep learning-based systems started to yield promising, high-quality results in the field of source separation. With this rapid emergence, the need for open-source datasets increased significantly. A deep learning algorithm generally tries to model a certain output distribution by computing the loss of a predicted output against its ground truth counterpart. Hence, training networks for source separation tasks requires the true sources to be fed to the model during training time. In the case of music source separation this means that the separated music stems are ideally available and free to use, which is often not the case due to the copyrighted constraints of this type of material.

Consequently, in 2016 *DSD100* [1] was introduced and made available to the public

and was later extended to *MUSDB18* [2], which comprises 150 full-length music tracks for a total of approximately 10 hours of music. To this day *MUSDB18* represents the largest freely available dataset of its kind. Although depicting various different musical styles, this dataset has a specific focus on four common musical sources: "vocals", "drums", "bass", and "others" (the last generally portrays musical parts whose nature may vary across songs, such as string, brass, or synthesizer parts). While such emphasis led to great improvements and promising results for many separation tasks performed on a mixture involving these common sources, the task of source separation for choral recordings remains to this day relatively unexplored and challenging.

1.1 Motivation

Although the task of source separation remains similar independently of the type of musical setting involved, the nature of the sources and their relations may entail various challenges and, consequently, may require different separation methodologies to be used (e.g. speech, music). Choir music constitutes a type of music composed for an ensemble of singers. A choir ensemble is usually structured by grouping the voices into four different sections, each depicting different frequency ranges; "Soprano" (260 Hz-880 Hz), "Alto" (190 Hz-660 Hz), "Tenor" (145 Hz-440 Hz), and "Bass" (90 Hz-290 Hz) [3]. Such structural setting is usually referred to as an SATB setting. Although different variants of this structure exist, this one is arguably the most common type and the one we will be focusing on in this work. While source separation for the pop/rock case has come leaps and bounds in the last few years, it remains largely unexplored for the SATB choir case, despite its cultural importance. This is partly due to the lack of a consolidated dataset, similar to the *MUSDB18*, and partly due to the nature of the task itself. The sources to be separated in pop/rock have distinct spectral structures; the voice is a harmonic instrument and has a distinct spectral shape, defined by a fundamental frequency and its harmonic partials and formants. The bass element to be separated also has a harmonic structure, but lacks the formants found in the human voice and has a

much lower fundamental frequency than the human voice.

(a) Spectrograms of isolated tenor and bass parts

(b) Spectrogram of the same tenor and bass parts mixed together

Figure 1: Spectrograms of tenor and bass parts, first isolated (Subfig. 1a), and then mixed together (Subfig. 1b). The mixture spectrogram depicts how correlated some of the parts' harmonics are.

(a) Spectrograms of two isolated common musical sources (Drums and Vocals).

(b) Spectrogram of the drums and vocal sources mixed together.

Figure 2: Spectrograms of drums and vocals sources, first isolated (Subfig. 2a) and then mixed together (Subfig. 2b). The mixture spectrogram depicts how uncorrelated the two original spectra are.

In contrast, the spectrum of a percussive instrument is generally inharmonic and

energy is usually spread across the spectrum. As opposed to common sources, the sources to be separated in an SATB choir all have a similar spectral structure with a fundamental frequency, partials and formants. This makes the task more challenging than its more studied counterpart. However, the distinct ranges of fundamental frequencies in the sources to be separated can be used to distinguish them from one another, a key aspect that we aim to explore in our study. Figs. 1 and 2 exemplify the discrepancy in source correlation between these two types of musical mixtures. In this work we attempt to address the challenges entailed by SATB mixtures for source separation by proposing an architecture aimed at segregating between the various SATB singing groups via spectral masking with the help of an external conditioning mechanism taking the sources' fundamental frequency contour as control input data. Fig. 3 depicts the overall pipeline that we will propose as part of this work.

Figure 3: Overview pipeline for SATB voice segregation proposed as part of this work.

1.2 Organization of the Thesis

This work is organized as follows: Chapter 2 presents and investigates some of the recently proposed high performance deep learning-based algorithms used for common musical source separation tasks, such as the U-Net [4] architecture and its

waveform-based adaptation, Wave-U-Net [5]. The same chapter then presents some of the metrics commonly used for evaluating these types of algorithms. Chapter 3 goes over the dataset curation carried out for this experiment as well as our adaptation of the conditioned U-Net model described in [6], which includes a control mechanism conditioned on the input sources' fundamental frequency (F0). Chapter 4 defines the evaluation metrics, methodology, as well as training and testing procedures used in this experiment. The same chapter then presents and discusses the evaluative and comparative results that we have gathered from the various models assessed in this work, specifically on the task of source separation for SATB recordings. Finally Chapter 5 concludes with a discussion around our experiment, its potential contributions towards the wider scope of audio source separation and provides comments on the type of future research that we intend to carry out.

Chapter 2

State-of-the-Art

In most source separation tasks involving deep learning, the original input sources are fed to a deep neural network which then reduces and compresses the original information by a significant amount, usually down to a bottleneck layer. These types of dimensionality reductions are most often an essential part of the process, allowing the network to learn deep representations of the original input signal. During the signal reconstruction stage, the model attempts to restore these deep feature representations back into their original states. Depending on the model architecture as well as the nature of the training data, among other factors as well, this last stage can be found quite challenging and may potentially lead to audio artifacts in the predicted output sources. A number of recent high-performing deep learning-based approaches are attempting to reduce this distortion problem by means of various strategies. While source separation has remained relatively unexplored for the case of SATB choirs, a number of architectures have been proposed over the last few years for musical source separation in the pop/rock case. A comprehensive overview of all proposed models is beyond the scope of this study, but we provide a summary of some of the most pertinent models that we believe can easily be adapted to the case in study. These architectures can be divided into two main categories: *spectrogram-based* source separation, which aims at separating a mixture spectrogram into its constituent sources through spectral masking and the more recent

category which entails the separation task to be directly performed in the *waveform domain*. Although this latter approach demonstrates more promising results overall, end-to-end architectures operating directly on the waveform usually require a substantial amount of training data.

2.1 Spectrogram-Based Audio Source Separation

Spectrogram-based source separation usually learns masks for each source. These spectral masks are then multiplied with the mixture’s spectrogram in order to predict the various source estimates from the input mixture (i.e. SATB groups in our case). The masks can either be binary assignment in $\{0, 1\}$ or soft assignment in $[0, 1]$. Generally speaking, for each source d_i of dimension $C \times N$ where $d_i \in [-1, 1]^{C \times N}$ a mask vector $m_i \in [0, 1]$ is calculated and applied to the input spectrogram mixture w . The final source estimate \hat{S}_j is then reconstructed by applying an inverse short-time Fourier Transform (ISTFT) operation on the masked spectrogram (see Eq. (2.1)). In this section, we will go over a few recent deep learning architectures implementing this approach.

$$\begin{aligned} d_i &= w \odot m_i, \\ \hat{S}_i &= ISTFT(d_i) \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

2.1.1 U-Net

A recent architecture that inspired many subsequent audio-related adaptations due to its unprecedented performance is the U-Net architecture, which was developed by Olaf Ronneberger et al. [4] to specifically process and segment biomedical images.

Architecture

The architecture itself resembles a classic auto-encoder and could arguably be called so. U-Net carries a contracting path (i.e. the encoding portion) which contains

Figure 4: U-Net architecture, including a contracting path (left portion), bottleneck (lower portion), expanding path (right portion), and skip connections (middle arrows) [4].

multiple convolutional layers that, each, computes the input's high-level features while reducing its receptive field (i.e. its initial time-context) in half through each of the layers. Past the last convolutional layer of the contracting path the feature maps are reduced to a linear representation of the initial input. In a traditional auto-encoder architecture this could be interpreted as the architecture bottleneck or latent space, which forces a highly compressed knowledge of the data. After the contraction stage, the expanding path (i.e. the decoder portion) fulfills two essential tasks: one of which aims at increasing the channels' receptive fields by up-sampling the feature maps through transposed convolutional layers, while the second task aims at concatenating the feature maps from the contracting path by means of skip connection layers. This latter step is a key element found in the U-Net architecture and is what differentiates a classic auto-encoder architecture, where some feature representations are lost past the bottleneck stage, from U-Net's. As a consequence, the architecture preserves the input dimensions on the output signal and both the receptive field as well as the channel dimensions are effectively represented.

Because the U-Net architecture was initially developed for image segmentation, the original model takes a 2D input; consequently, a direct adaptation of such a model

specifically targeting audio signals would need to operate at the same dimension level (e.g. by using the input's power spectrogram). Several adaptations of the U-Net model directed towards musical signals have already been proposed, all operating at the spectrogram level [7, 8, 9]. It is to note that source separation carried out in the time-frequency domain should be approached carefully; when the signal to be reconstructed by the model consists of images, pixel-displacement may have little to no impact on the visual perception of the results, however the same would not apply for audio signals; due to the human logarithmic perception of audio, pixel distortion in the output can become perceptually much more dramatic. U-Net is a particularly appealing architecture for tasks involving audio signals since the skip connection layers previously mentioned help transmitting low-level information directly to the decoding path and thus substantially improve the output's accuracy.

2.1.2 U-Net Spectrogram

One of the first papers to present the idea of U-Net adaptation towards audio source separation tasks was [8], in which vocal separation applied to western commercial music (i.e. Pop music) was specifically targeted. In this work, the authors proposed an architecture directly derived from the original U-Net one, which predicted a soft-mask of the targeted source (either vocal or instrumental source). The predicted mask was then multiplied element-wise with the mixture spectrogram in order to obtain the wanted isolated source. Fig. 5 depicts such an architecture, where a mixture spectrogram is input into the U-Net network, a spectral mask targeting the source is then predicted and multiplied element-wise with the original input spectrogram (depicted by the "Multiply" connection). The loss function of the training process is given by Eq. (2.2), where the predicted mask is θ , the input mixture X , and the predicted source is given by Y .

$$L(X, Y; \theta) = \|f(X, \theta) \odot X - Y\| \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 5: U-Net architecture proposed as part of [8] for spectrogram-based singing voice separation.

It is worth mentioning that for each given source (in this case θ_v for the vocal and θ_i for the instrumental), a U-Net instance is trained in order to predict their respective mask. In the case of SATB mixtures, four U-Net instances will be necessary in order to predict each of the four singing groups.

2.1.3 Conditioned Network

Initially developed towards computer vision tasks, network conditioning has gained a tremendous amount of success towards audio-related tasks over the past few years; the paradigm not only helps the model to improve its performance but also lowers the overall computational cost by reducing the number of parameters by a noticeable amount. Generally speaking, conditioned learning divides an architecture into two components; a generic system as well as an external control mechanism that directs its behavior based on external data Fig. 6 depicts the high-level duality between a traditional architecture and its conditioned counterpart.

Although conditioning has mainly been used in image processing fields, the concept recently started to be employed in MIR and audio-related tasks as well, for instance in speech generation [10] or speech recognition [11]. The paradigm has also been adapted to source separation tasks, for instance by having a control mechanism

(a) Traditional approach: each source to be separated from the mix requires its own trained model.

(b) Approach proposed in [6] with a generic model and control mechanism for conditioning learning

Figure 6: Traditional architecture (Subfig. 6a) and its conditioned architecture counterpart (Subfig. 6b).

adapting a generic model to separate a specific instrument in the given mix. In [6], the authors propose a conditioned architecture based on U-Net.

2.1.4 Conditioning in Audio

The spectrogram-based U-Net adaptation described earlier trains a separate model for each of the mixture sources. Depending on the nature of the separation task, this can easily lead to scaling issues. The conditioned U-Net (C-U-Net) architecture, described in [6], aims at addressing this limitation by introducing a control mechanism in turn controlled by external data which would then govern a single U-Net instance. The proposed architecture does not diverge much from the initial U-Net one; as an alternative to the multiple instances of the model, each of which is specialized in isolating a specific source, C-U-Net proposes the insertion of feature-wise linear modulation (*FiLM*) layers [12] across the architecture. This allows the application of linear transformations to intermediate features, based on the source to separate. These specialized layers maintain the shape of the original intermediate

feature input while modifying the underlying mapping of the filters themselves.

$$FiLM(x) = \gamma(\bar{z}) \cdot x + \beta(\bar{z}) \quad (2.3)$$

In Eq. (2.3), x is the input of the *FiLM* layer, γ and β the learnable parameters that scale and shift x based on an external information, \bar{z} . γ and β modulates the feature maps according to an input vector \bar{z} , which describes the source to separate. The condition generator block described in Fig. 7a represents a neural network which embeds the one-hot encoding input \bar{z} into the most optimal values to be used by the *FiLM* layers.

Conditioned U-Net Architecture

Although the network filters can be modulated at any level in the architecture, in [6] the authors opt to insert the conditioning layer between the batch normalization stage and the *Leaky ReLu* activation function of the downsampling path blocks (Fig. 7b). Applying this layer after the normalization is an essential step as it allows the filters to truly specialize themselves in their respective tasks without being affected by the normalization operation. Moreover, having the output of each encoding U-Net blocks shifted and scaled by the *FiLM* layer results in the modulated feature maps to be carried by the U-Net skip connections with their respective transformation.

The C-U-Net architecture works in similar ways as described in [10], with two different types of *FiLM* layers; one operating at a global level by applying the same affine transformation to the entirety of the feature maps while the other works at the local level by modulating each feature map independently (Fig. 8). The former layer is referred to as a *FiLM simple* layer and entails two transform scalars per layer, for a total of 12 parameters (6 γ , 6 β) while the latter, referred to as *FiLM complex* layer, includes a set of transformation parameters for each feature map in the downsampling path, totaling in 2016 parameters (1008 γ , 1008 β).

This latter type of conditioning, while being computationally more expensive, should

(a) C-U-Net control mechanism with the vector \bar{z} , a one-hot representation of the source to separate, which dictates the N sets of γ and β values to be used by the *FiLM* layer at each of the block of the encoding path, 1 to N .

(b) *FiLM* layer incorporated into the U-Net encoding block

Figure 7: C-U-Net control mechanism with *FiLM* incorporated into the encoding blocks

theoretically allow for a better specialization and thus a better separation performance. However in practice the results show that the *FiLM simple* layer performs as well as its more complex counterpart.

Although the control mechanism used in this preliminary experiment is governed by the various instruments present in the recording (expressed through \bar{z} as a one-hot encoded vector), there is no restriction as to what type of data can be fed to the condition generator. Any external data that is deemed useful to discriminate between the various sources is a viable option. In this view, we will opt to reproduce the experiment in [6] this time targeting choral singing specifically, by conditioning

Figure 8: Simple vs. Complex affine transformations proposed as part of the C-U-Net Architecture [6].

the network on the F0 tracks from each sources present in the recording. The approach will be described in greater detail in Section 3.

2.1.5 Open-Unmix

Similarly to what has been covered so far, the Open-Unmix (UMX) [13] architecture proposes a spectrogram-based DNN model for musical source separation. Unlike the previous models reported in this section, UMX implements a bidirectional LSTM at its core. The model’s main aims are to deliver state-of-the-art results while maintaining a fairly intuitive and easy-to-understand architecture. The model is therefore simple to extend and delivers SOTA performance on common musical source separation. With this in mind, we will opt to assess our task with Open-Unmix as well.

Architecture

The core idea behind UMX consists of a multi-layers bidirectional long short-term memory (BiLSTM) architecture which predicts the spectrogram of a target source from a given mixture by capturing long term dependencies on input spectrogram frames. The model is thus operating in both the time and frequency domains in order to predict the sources of a given mixture. No other model covered in this work so far has implemented this type of temporal behavior as part of its architecture. This in itself seems to help increase the model’s performance by a great amount (see section 2.4). As BiLSTM-based architecture learns from past and future information, UMX

cannot be utilized in a real-time context, which fortunately doesn't affect us.

The input to the model can either be a spectrogram or a waveform, however since the model operates at the spectrogram level, the short-time Fourier Transform (STFT) will internally be computed from the input in the latter case. A high level of the UMX architecture is shown through Fig. 9. The dimensions (frequency and channel) of the spectrogram input are reduced prior to feeding it to the BiLSTM network (`fc1`), which will then treat the feature maps as sequential data along the time axis. LSTM networks can add to the overall architecture size very quickly, moreover these types of architectures are computationally costly. Hence, reducing the input dimension prior to feeding it to the network allows for faster loss convergence as well as a lighter architecture.

It is worth mentioning that like the U-Net architecture, UMX uses skip connections between the BiLSTM input and output stages to maintain the structural integrity of the initial input spectrogram. The output of the BiLSTM block consists of a fully connected dense layer which is then decoded back into its original dimension (`fc2`, `fc3`). As a last step, the full-band masks are applied to the original spectrogram input mixture through the multiplicative skip connection depicted in Fig. 9. Similar to the spectrogram-based U-Net architecture covered in Subsection 2.1.2, the same type of loss function (Eq. (2.2)) will be used in order to learn the magnitude masks and ultimately obtain the predicted isolated sources from the given mixture.

Although these spectrogram-based approaches return promising results and require much less data compared to waveform-based architectures (i.e. Wave-U-Net), they do contain some architectural flaws which can limit their performance on both analysis as well as synthesis ends and ultimately add another layer of latency to the overall process. In an optimal scenario, when performing a musical source separation task on an input spectrogram, the STFT parameters should be tailored according to the nature of the sources themselves, which is an aspect that is usually overlooked. Moreover, most SOTA architectures described in this section leave out the phase portion of the signal during the training process and attempt to reconstruct the output signal using only the energy information of each of the sources. Consequently,

Figure 9: Open-Unmix architecture, which implements a biLSTM architecture at its core. The skip connections can be seen at different level of the architecture between the pre and post-biLSTM portion [13].

the synthesis process uses the phase of the *original signal* (i.e. of the original input mixture) [6, 8] for the waveform reconstruction. This approach can be described as valid assuming that the original sources are sparsely distributed across the frequency bins. On the other hand, if two or more sources happen to be active as part of the same bin, the resulting estimation may be biased. In the case of choir music, where the sources happen to be largely correlated, it is not uncommon to find multiple singing groups to be active as part of the same spectral bin due to high correlation, consequently this reconstruction approach can become more problematic, even more than for the case involving common musical sources.

Alternatively numerous phase reconstruction techniques have been proposed in order to overcome this issue [14, 15], most of which are based on the *Griffin-Lim* algorithm [16].

Due to the U-Net’s novel architecture and promising performance, but also the constraints and flaws implied by the spectrogram approaches described above, a U-Net adaptation was developed, Wave-U-Net [5], which proposes an end-to-end architecture operating directly in the waveform domain. Such architecture have the potential to lift some of the above-mentioned limitations since there are no synthesis steps involved in the loss generation process, consequently, all the steps are accounted for during the loss training process.

2.2 Convolutional Time-Domain Audio Source Separation

The recent emergence of large music datasets [1, 2] made available to the public, have allowed models, such as waveform-based ones which require more data than their spectrogram-based counterparts, to become a feasible approach for source separation tasks. Such models include end-to-end architectures taking raw time-domain information as their input, without requiring any kind of pre- or post-processing steps to be taken. As the input is a one-dimensional signal, the feature maps are computed directly from the waveform samples through 1D convolution operations. The output source predictions are also expected to be in the time-domain. Wave-U-Net [5], Demucs [9], and Conv-Tasnet [17] all belong to this same category of models, however, the last two models suffer from architectural trade-off; Conv-Tasnet attempts to minimize performance latency for real-time speech separation applications while Demucs' architecture size exceeds by far what our current computer setup would be able to handle, yielding nearly a total of 650mio parameters against an average of 10mio for the model that we will be considering in this work. Consequently, we opt to experiment with the former model, Wave-U-Net, which yields similar results comparable to state-of-the-art waveform-based models.

2.2.1 Wave-U-Net

Architecture

In [5], the authors present a time-domain adaptation of the U-Net architecture, which performs the separation operation on the waveform. As the input is a one-dimensional signal, the feature maps are computed directly from the waveform samples through 1D convolution operations. Consequently, the feature maps along both contracting and expanding paths are computed by means of single-dimensional convolution layers. Both paths contain twelve convolutional layers, each, for a total of 24 layers. In the down-sampling path, the receptive field, or time-context dimension, is reduced in half after each layer, to the benefit of an increase of the input

Figure 10: Wave-U-Net architecture proposed as part of [5]. The network performs the separation directly in the waveform domain through 1D convolution operations.

feature maps by 24 every time. On the other hand, in the up-sampling path the time-context is doubled after every convolutional layer while the feature maps are reduced, again by 24, at every layers. Through this mean, the receptive field and the number of channels of the original input signal will remain preserved in the output.

In image processing, the use of transposed convolution as an up-sampling mean has proven to produce a substantial amount of distortion in the resulting signal [18]. As a consequence, Wave-U-Net implements linear interpolation as its up-sampling method, which promotes feature continuity. Although not ideal, linear interpolation has proven to prevent the presence of unwanted high-frequency components that transposed convolution would produce in the final output layer. The last convolutional layer of the model outputs a map of shape $[inputframesize, 26]$ where 26 is the number of feature maps that will ultimately be collapsed into the targeted

number of output channels (e.g. mono or stereo). This final contraction will be carried out by mean of one-by-one convolution operations, which will reduce the 26 remaining features maps down to K predicted sources, each of them represented by K unique feature maps summations. Lastly, a hyperbolic tangent activation function, which will constrain the output within a $[-1, 1]$ range (suitable for audio data), will be applied to the K sources. The loss calculation will be based on the mean square error (MSE) computed between the predicted sources and the true source.

Alternatively, Wave-U-Net proposes an improvement to the original output layer which enforces an energy conservation loss on the output. Hence, the model assumes a linear additivity property to the data, which is a fair assumption when it comes to audio mixture and has proved to improve the performance in many other audio-related tasks as well, such as in speech de-noising [19]. To this end, the difference output layer adds an additional constraint to the K output sources and enforces the following:

$$\sum_{j=1}^K \hat{S}^j = M \quad (2.4)$$

Consequently in this alternate approach only $K - 1$ one-by-one convolutional filters will be applied to the last feature maps while the K th source will be computed as follows:

$$\hat{S}^K = M - \sum_{j=1}^{K-1} \hat{S}^j \quad (2.5)$$

Although Wave-U-Net has proven to deliver satisfying results on common musical source separation tasks, the fact remains that waveform-based architectures in general require more data than their spectrogram-based counterparts.

Figure 11: Wave-U-Net output layer details, including last skip connection, concatenation, one-by-one convolution, and \tanh activation function.

2.3 Audio Source Separation Metrics

With the rapid emergence of models and algorithms targeting audio source separations tasks (statistical ones and more recently, deep learning approaches as well), the need for standardized measurement metrics arose. With the lack of common objective evaluation metrics, assessment of source separation tasks and algorithm comparisons were found to be a challenging process. The goal of such an assessment is to ultimately measure the difference (perceptual or mathematical) between a predicted and a true source, that is to measure how different the predicted source could be perceived by a listener in comparison to its original counterpart. While subjective evaluations succeed in addressing important auditory aspects that objective approaches fail to model, such as loudness weighting or spectral masking, they have not represented quantifiable metrics up until very recently [20] and have rarely been used in the context of source separation evaluation. While subjective approaches compensate for their lack of consistency by giving better perceptual accuracy, the objective ones accommodate for better reproducibility and consistency across experiments.

2.3.1 Previous Evaluation Methods and Limitations

The following subsection aims at providing context and background with respect to the current state of objective measurement methods. A successful attempt at standardizing evaluation metrics for audio source separation tasks was made through [21] and then further established in [22]. The proposed metrics specifically target the performance of source separation algorithms, calling for scenarios in which there is little to no prior knowledge about the sources and/or the underlying mixing process employed in the separation process. Expressing a mixture x consisting of N sources and recorded by M sensors as follows:

$$x = A * s + n \tag{2.6}$$

where A represents the mixing system $M \times N$, s the vector of sources, and n the added noise signal. In a determined mixture scenario where N and M are equivalent (i.e. square mixture matrix), a demixing system W can conveniently be recovered as: $W = A^{-1}$

Such scenarios could include two speakers recorded as part of a stereo signal or a signal recorded with microphone arrays, which doesn't relate to our task. In an under-determined scenario where the number of sensors is smaller than the number of sources (i.e. $M < N$), such as in our case (e.g. multiple singers recorded as part of a monoaural recording) the problem becomes more complex as $x = A * s$ contains an *affine* set of solutions.

Prior source separation evaluation methodologies, such as Inter-Symbol Interference [23] necessitate the use of a global system $B = W * A$ which verifies $\hat{s} = B * s$. That is, the measured quality of the predicted source relies on the definition of a general time-invariant linear de-mixing system, which can't be a feasible assumption in the context of our task.

2.3.2 Current Objective Measurement Methods

In order to overcome the evaluation limitations introduced by the complexity of the cases described in the previous section, the following metrics, which are based on *non-perceptual* energy ratios, have been proposed as part of [21] and made available, first through the BSS Eval toolkit ¹, and later integrated to the *mir_eval toolbox* ² [24], which is one of the evaluation frameworks that we will be using in this work.

SDR, SIR, SAR:

Namely, Signal-to-distortion, signal-to-artifacts, and signal-to-interference ratios depict various ways of computing the performance of audio source separation algorithms by decomposing the predicted source into the following sum of its compo-

¹ BSS Eval: A toolbox for performance measurement in (blind) source separation:
http://bass-db.gforge.inria.fr/bss_eval/

² *mir_eval*: A Transparent Implement of Common MIR Metrics:
http://craffel.github.io/mir_eval/#module-mir_eval.io

nents:

$$\hat{s} = s_{target} + e_{interf} + e_{noise} + e_{artif} \quad (2.7)$$

The decomposition formulated above attempts to convey numerical insights about the quality of a predicted source with respect to its true and original source counterpart, from various different perspectives. s_{target} is the original source s modified by a certain amount of distortion, which can be depicted by the function f , such as $s_{target} = f(s)$, e_{interf} , e_{noise} , e_{artif} all represent errors terms generated from other unwanted sources: respectively the amount of interference between unwanted and wanted source, the amount of distortion found in the unwanted source (i.e. noise), and finally the amount of artifacts introduced by the separation algorithm itself. The signal-to-distortion and interference ratios (SDR and SIR) are then computed with respect to the true signal, as follows (it is important to note that each of these metrics are expressed in decibels in an attempt at depicting the human auditory perception at its best):

$$SDR := 10\log_{10} + \frac{\|S_{target}\|^2}{\|e_{interf} + e_{noise} + e_{artif}\|^2} \quad (2.8)$$

$$SIR := 10\log_{10} + \frac{\|S_{target}\|^2}{\|e_{interf}\|^2} \quad (2.9)$$

Where the SDR metric measures the global quality, involving all the audio impairments, while SIR represents the quality as a ratio between the wanted and unwanted sources.

2.3.3 Recent Emergence of Subjective Evaluation Methods

The BSS Eval metrics covered in the previous section have been widely used in order to assess audio source separation task performances [5, 17, 9, 13, 6]. However, in some cases these metrics will fail to convey the proper perceptual qualities of the

resulting predictions, such as assessing speech intelligibility or in tasks involving the predictions of raw, unprocessed stems [25]. In the case of SATB voice segregation, there are many important aspects that these metrics may not accurately convey, such as the preservation of elocution, intelligibility, as well as word articulation. With this in mind, subjective approaches have been proposed [20], which attempt to carry certain perceptual aspects of audio signals that traditional objective metrics will fail to address, under the form of listening tests, for example [26].

PEASS - Perceptually-Motivated Objective Scores

PEASS [27] or *Perceptual Evaluation method for Audio Source Separation* is the perceptually-motivated counterpart of the BSS Eval toolkit. PEASS aims at providing objective metrics, which are built on top of subjective scores. In the first stage of PEASS, three types of distortion are extracted from the predicted sources: SDR, SIR, and SAR. These distortion components are then fed into a PEMO-Q auditory model [28] which estimates their respective salience (i.e. their perceived auditory prominence). These perceptually-motivated metrics are then fed into a neural networks trained on human-data, based on the four following criteria: global quality, preservation of the target source, suppression of other sources, and absence of additional artifacts. In a final stage, the four different features gathered from the PEMO-Q model (Eq. (2.10)), will be combined in a non-linear way through subjective scale mappings in order to predict the final objective scores, namely the Overall Perceptual Score (OPS), the Target-related Perceptual Score (TPS), the Interference-related Perceptual Score (IPS), and the Artifacts-related Perceptual Score (APS).

$$\begin{aligned}
 q_j^{overall} &\triangleq PSM(\hat{s}_j, s_j), \\
 q_j^{target} &\triangleq PSM(\hat{s}_j, s_j - e_j^{target}), \\
 q_j^{interf} &\triangleq PSM(\hat{s}_j, s_j - e_j^{interf}), \\
 q_j^{artif} &\triangleq PSM(\hat{s}_j, s_j - e_j^{artif})
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.10}$$

BSS Eval and PEASS

While both evaluation methods have the same aim, that is assessing the performance of a separation algorithm through audio quality assessments, both differ substantially in their approaches. Comparative experiments have been hitherto inconclusive as to which one addresses the matter of perceptual relevance better when it comes to a separation task. [29] presents an experiment which consisted in computing the correlation of the two evaluation scores against human ratings while specifically targeting singing voice separation signals. The two subjectively-measured perceptual attributes consisted in the overall sound quality as well as the level of interference found in the predicted sources. Fig. 12 depicts the resulting correlation measured between the objective measurements and the mean of the subjective ratings.

Figure 12: PEASS and BSS Eval objective measures correlated to subjective ratings [29].

Through the correlation analysis depicted in Fig. 12, we observe that the APS (Artifacts-related Perceptual Score) metric from the PEASS toolkit has the highest correlation with subjective judgement and therefore may hold the strongest predictive capability for source separation performance evaluation. Close behind we also note that both the IPS (Interference-related Perceptual Score) as well as the SIR

metrics show comparable correlations with the interference ratings.

MUSHRA Listening Test

The previous measurement approaches covered in this section all involve some sort of objective method, whether or not the resulting metrics are motivated by subjective qualities (PEASS) or not (BSS Eval), the separation performance remains assessed by an algorithm as opposed to human assessment. In this view, a third, fully subjective, type of audio assessment is also presented in this section, which calls for subjective audio qualities as reported by human test subjects. The MUSHRA [30] (Multiple Stimulus with Hidden Reference and Anchors) test procedure consists in the assessment of the quality degradation of a given test signal based on a known reference, usually referred to as higher anchor. The rating scale spans from 0 to 100 and is divided into five quality intervals, namely “excellent”, “good”, “fair”, “poor” and “bad”. The quality aspects to be rated should be carefully picked according to the nature of the sources to assess. Indeed in a scenario where the source to be separated is either singing voice or speech, features like intelligibility and elocution may turn out to be an essential element of the aspect to rate. In a musical context where all the sources involved are voices, such as ours, the content of the predictions as well as how close to a single voice the predictions sound, will be crucial factors to take into consideration. While subjective listening tests such as MUSHRA may arguably be more perceptually valid than objective measurements, they are also more difficult to conduct.

Beside the reproducibility limitation entailed by the nature of the test, one additional challenge relates to the logistics of the test itself; it can indeed be quite time-consuming and costly to gather enough test subjects in order to obtain statistically significant results. Not only that but in an ideal scenario the subjects would need to be trained for the task in order to avoid critical differences in the ratings to the greatest possible extent.

In this work, we opt to measure our approaches using the three above-mentioned evaluation strategies, that is the BSS Eval toolkit, the PEASS toolkit and finally by

conducting subjective listening tests as well. More discussion around our evaluation methodologies on SATB choir recordings can be found in Chapter 4.1.

2.4 Preliminary Results on Common Sources

In this section we briefly present some preliminary results regarding the separation task performed on the four common musical sources, namely "Vocal", "Drums", "Bass", and "Others", performed by the four models previously described. To the best of our knowledge there are no previous works specifically targeting choral recordings. As our task targets SATB mixtures, this prevents us from drawing a proper comparison between our approach and the SOTA ones. We, however, still deem useful and relevant to include the BSS Eval results below as a reference.

Model	Domain	Test SDR (dB)				
		Vocal	Drums	Bass	Others	Average
Wave-U-Net	Waveform	3.25	4.22	3.21	2.25	3.23
U-Net Spectrogram	Spectrogram	4.72	4.13	2.48	0.97	3.08
Open-Unmix	Spectrogram	6.32	5.73	5.23	4.02	5.36
C-U-Net	Spectrogram	4.65	4.38	2.60	1.71	3.34

Table 1: SDR results (Vocal, Drums, Bass, Others, Average) for all four models described in this Chapter.

Table 1 shows the SDR results for all four models previously described. As depicted, Open-Unmix seems to outperform all three other models (namely Wave-U-Net, U-Net, and C-U-Net) across all source categories, with a substantial average increase of about 2.14dB SDR against the other models' SDR average. We also observe that U-Net falls behind its waveform-based counterpart, Wave-U-Net. Part of the reason might be related to the appropriate size of the train-set used to efficiently train the model. As described earlier, the training of waveform-based models such as Wave-U-Net requires much more data compared to training on spectrogram-based ones. The SDR results from the C-U-Net model don't show substantial improvements from its plain counterpart, U-Net spectrogram. As previously mentioned, we plan

to condition a U-Net architecture with the F0 tracks from the various SATB sources. We hope that by doing so, the results will show greater improvements than the ones observed above.

Since all the models described in Table 1 have been trained on the MUSDB18 dataset [2], which represents a much larger dataset as compared to ours, the same results may not yield for our task. We speculate that, unlike the observation made above, Wave-U-Net won't perform nearly as well as its spectrogram counterpart and other mask-based models since our datasets are much more limited in size (see Section 3.1).

Deep learning-based methods have been progressing at a substantially fast pace for the last few years, consequently many DNN architectures tailored specifically towards audio source separation tasks have been proposed. There are numerous other models out there yielding similar, not to say better results than the few architectures covered in this work [9, 17, 31]. We opted to assess our task against the architectures included as part of Table 1 based on criteria such as adaptability to our task, amount of training data required, and architecture size.

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Dataset Curation

The training data we have curated for this experiment are composed of the following datasets:

- Choral Singing Dataset [32]. Three songs performed by 16 singers from the Anton Bruckner Choir. (SATB) ¹.
- Proprietary dataset including 26 songs for exactly one singer per part.

There are very few publicly available choir music datasets, thus our choice remains limited. To this day and to the best of our knowledge, there isn't any existing dataset which is specifically suited to our task, therefore one of the subsidiary work of this experiment revolves around curating a proper and complete dataset to train our various models. For our experiment, we take advantage of the Choral Singing Dataset [32]. This dataset was recorded in a professional studio and contains individual tracks for each of the 16 singers of a SATB choir, i.e. 4 singers per choir section. It comprises three different choral pieces: *Locus Iste*, written by Anton Bruckner, *N̄no Dios d'Amor Herido*, written by Francisco Guerrero, and *El Rossinyol*, a Catalan popular song; all of them were written for 4-part mixed choir. The dataset is

¹<https://zenodo.org/record/1286570#.XyGcHy-z3yU>

very well suited for our experiment as the isolated track for each individual singer will allow us to proceed the same way as in [33], that is to create artificial mixes by combining various stems from different groups. Using different combinations of all 16 singers, we created 256 SATB quartets for each piece, which represent all possible combinations of singers, taking into account the voice type restriction (i.e. *exactly* one singer per voice is needed).

The second dataset we opt to use is a proprietary one including 26 songs for exactly one singer per part (i.e. 4 stems per song), which is a well-suited format for our task as well.

A third available proprietary dataset containing four different songs of different numbers of takes each, for a total of 17 unique takes, was also considered for this experiment but won't be used due to the poor conditions in which the recordings of the data have been produced; the individual stems do indeed display important signs of spill, resulting in each isolated part containing a substantial amount of information from other parts as well. In order to verify that this data would undeniably impair our model training, we trained two versions of U-Net: a first one including all three datasets and a second one excluding this last proprietary dataset. The results confirmed that including the dataset as part of the training data does doubtlessly worsen the resulting models' inference by about 0.5dB SDR.

In view of this, we deem that the underlying clean-up and formatting work for this dataset is too important for the scope of this work and we will leave this task for future work improvements.

Our curation work consists in consolidating these two datasets and making sure that all the data that we are using remain consistent and well-formatted across all the audio stems, which includes length and amplitude normalization, as well as properties standardization. Most of the files included as part of the initial datasets were presented as 10-seconds long snippets as opposed to full-length songs, which isn't an ideal format to work with. Hence, some additional efforts have been devoted to turn these files into a more convenient and consolidated format. By bringing a con-

siderable effort into collecting, consolidating and cleaning these datasets specifically for this task, we hope that, despite the limited size of our datasets, we will be able to get the most out of them.

3.2 Approach

Injecting domain knowledge in DNNs has been proved to be an effective way to learn complex input-output relations with high accuracy, especially when the available data happen to be scarce and limited [34], such as found in our case.

Each of the singing groups in SATB recordings performs within its own respective frequency range, that is, the voices' F0 contour will rarely overlap across the various neighboring groups' singing range. This factor makes the sources' F0 a suitable *discriminative* feature, which could be injected in the DNN during the training stage and, potentially, improve the model inference towards the separation of the various singing groups in SATB recordings.

To this end, we propose to adapt the original C-U-Net architecture, which initially embeds the instruments to be separated, \bar{z} , in order to produce the various *FiLM* parameters (γ, β) , and substitute the external control input data for the F0 track of the target source. The new resulting control input vector \bar{z} will thus hold both time as well as frequency dimensions. We will henceforth refer to our proposed models as being *domain-specific* as they take into account information conveyed by the sources in order to improve the training process, while the models presented in Chapter 2 will be referred to as *domain-agnostic* models.

3.2.1 Control Input Representation

As previously mentioned, we use the frame-wise F0 as the external control data of our condition generator network. This entails a few required preliminary steps to be taken prior to proceeding to the training stage. We first automatically extract the sources' F0 track using the DIO algorithm ² [35]. Once the raw pitch tracks

²<https://github.com/mmorise/World>

are obtained, we convert each time-step F0 into a one-hot encoded representation as postulated in [36], that is 60 frequency bins over 6 musical octaves, with a base frequency of 32.7 Hz, for a total of 360 frequency bins per time-step. The implementation of the DIO algorithm in [35] reports the silent and unpitched frames as *NaN* values: to simplify the handling and learning of the data by the control model, we opt to replace all the values reported as such with 0's instead.

As a result, for an input spectrogram containing 128 time-steps, our control input will be in the shape of [128, 360].

3.2.2 Control Model

Our proposed approach consists in four variants of the C-U-Net architecture, each differing slightly, first in the way they embed the control input data, but also in the way the resulting parameters are injected into the main network. In this subsection we go over the details of these variants.

Pre-Encoding and Post-Decoding Conditioning

The control model used in our proposed architecture embeds the one-hot encoded CQT F0 representation for a given time-step into a set of transforms whose shape is either partly or fully identical to the input spectrogram. This is achieved by modeling the condition vectors as 1-D data with multiple feature channels. The condition vectors are then fed into a convolutional neural network (CNN) with a kernel of size 10 which seizes contextual information from the adjacent time-steps. As a result, all input channels from the initial convolution contribute to all resulting feature maps in the output of the first convolutional layer. Finally a dense layer provides a specific type of conditioning to be applied to the input spectrogram, taking into account the contextual information previously captured by the CNN filters. Fig. 14 shows the condition generator architecture in greater detail.

As the temporal relationships between the external control input data and the input spectrogram are closely intertwined, it is crucial to apply these affine transformations while the receptive field of the input is still intact. Hence the *FiLM* layer is applied

Figure 13: C-U-Net control mechanism adapted to our task; the one-hot vector \bar{z} depicts the various SATB singing groups’ F0 contour.

prior to the encoding path. Fig. 13 shows the overall structure behind the proposed conditioning architecture.

We propose three variants of the architecture described above. The first one applies a single transform for all frequency bins at a given time-step, resulting in a set of scalars of shape $(\gamma(128, 1), \beta(128, 1))$ on the output of the control model. The second variant applies a unique affine transform for each individual frequency bin at every input time-step. Consequently the number of affine transforms is increased by the number of input frequency bins and results in the following control model output shape: $(\gamma(128, 512), \beta(128, 512))$. Finally, our third approach borrows the same pattern as that of the second variant, but applies its transform at both the input and output levels. This results in the doubling of the amount of scalars codified by the control input model and results in two sets of $(\gamma(128, 512), \beta(128, 512))$.

We refer to these three approaches as *Local*, *Global* and *Global x2*, respectively. Fig. 14 depicts the underlying architecture behind these three approaches in greater detail.

Figure 14: The three variants of the control model architecture for three of our four proposed models. The convolution is performed across the frequency bins (treated as feature channels) for each time-step. At the output stage the dense layer(s) provides various numbers of scalars. *Local conditioning* embeds the target source’s F0 into 2 scalars per time-step. *Global conditioning* codifies the F0 into a set of scalars for each frequency bin per input time-step. Lastly *Global x2 conditioning* does it at both input and output levels.

Encoding Conditioning

Our fourth and last variant diverges slightly from our three former adaptations in both the way the target source’s F0 is embedded but also in the way the resulting scalars are used in the main network. This time instead of applying the transforms to the original input spectrogram (i.e. either pre-encoding or post-decoding), we apply the transform to the intermediary features maps inside the encoding path. Consequently, as in this scenario the preservation of the time-context is not as crucial anymore, we opt to embed the control input vector \bar{z} through a *multilayer perceptron* (MLP) consisting of three Dense layer of 16, 64, and 256 neurons and two final Dense layers outputting respectively $N\beta$ and $N\gamma$, where N is the number of blocks in the encoding path. Fig. 15 depicts the underlying architecture behind this last variant in greater detail.

Figure 15: Control model architecture used in our fourth proposed adaptation of C-U-Net; *C-U-Net Encoder conditioning*. In this fourth variant, the target source’s F0 is embedded through a MLP into N sets of γ and β values to be used by the *FiLM* layer at each block of the encoding path, 1 to N .

Chapter 4

Experiment

4.1 Evaluation

To assess our proposed approach and show that injecting domain knowledge as control input data to the network improves its performance on SATB recordings, we evaluated the performances of the four domain-agnostic state-of-the-art DNN models covered in Chapter 2; U-Net, its waveform adaptation Wave-U-Net, Open-Unmix (UMIX), and the original C-U-Net, referred to below as *C-U-Net Domain-Agnostic* or *C-U-Net D-A*. We then compared the results against our results, delivered by the four domain-specific models described in Section 3.2. We measured the performance of a model by computing three different sets of measurements, going from fully objective to fully subjective ones (see Subsection 2.3).

4.1.1 Train - Test Dataset Split

Given the limited nature of our datasets, we opted to train the various models with mixtures involving *exactly* one singer per voice (i.e. quartets). We then tested the models against two different test sets; the first set corresponded to four 4-singers songs (quartet), which depicted the type of mixture that the models would have been trained on; in order to build our first use-case test set, we set apart one song from the proprietary dataset as well as one singer per voice for each song from the

CSD for a total of four songs. The rest of the data was used for training. This allowed us to evaluate the model on unseen songs and singers. Our second test case contained unison singing, which was not seen at all during training. As such, we used the three songs from the CSD with all singers (16 in total) for evaluation.

4.1.2 Training

All the models' trainings and inferences have been performed with audio data re-sampled at 22 050 Hz. While this sampling rate does not cover the full human hearing range and may consequently discard some information that the audio data may convey, it allowed us to substantially reduce the computation time and therefore facilitated the training of the numerous models (8 in total) in the context of this work. Because of the lack of available data, we opted to validate our model's performance during training time on our first use-case's test set. In an optimal scenario a test set should be fully decoupled from the model training stage. In our case, proceeding in such way allowed us to obtain an accurate indication of the models' performance on our test set directly during the model training. The data generation process used a batch generator function that we have designed for the scope of this work. The process looks into a HDF5 file which stores the entirety of our two datasets. Resampling and *pre*-loading the data into this convenient format as a pre-processing step allowed us to avoid any potential computation overhead that we might otherwise have encountered during the training stage. The batch generator function then creates random mixes of fixed length. For models taking additional condition vectors as input, the external data (e.g. F0 matrices for our models) are retrieved from pre-computed serialized *.pkl* files and added as part of the batch as well (see Table 2 for more details on models' input dimension). Our four domain-specific models' implementation ¹ have been built on top of the original C-U-Net implementation ², initially proposed as part of [6]. Lastly, the training was done on a computer with GeForce GTX TITAN X GPU, Intel Core i7-5820K 3.3GHz 6-Core Processor, X99 gaming 5 x99 ATX DDR4 motherboard.

¹Our adapted Conditioned-U-Net architectures: <https://github.com/darius522/cunet>

²Original Conditioned-U-Net architecture: <https://github.com/gabolsgabs/cunet>

Model	Dom.	# Params	# Epochs	Input	Cond.
<i>Wave-U-Net</i>	Wav	10.2M	248	[16384 × 1]	N/A
<i>U-Net</i>	Spec	9.8M × 4	228	[128, 512]	N/A
<i>Open-Unmix</i>	Spec	8.9M × 4	192	[128, 2048]	N/A
<i>C-U-Net D-A</i>	Spec	10.4M	175	[128, 512]	[4, 1]

<i>C-U-Net D-S L</i>	Spec	10.1M	200	[128, 512]	[128, 360]
<i>C-U-Net D-S G</i>	Spec	10.3M	182	[128, 512]	[128, 360]
<i>C-U-Net D-S G x2</i>	Spec	10.0M	215	[128, 512]	[128, 360]
<i>C-U-Net D-S Enc</i>	Spec	10.5M	200	[128, 512]	[128, 360]

Table 2: Comparison table depicting the various models (4 domain-agnostic and 4 domain-specific (ours)) trained and assessed as part of our experiment.

4.1.3 Testing

We performed two series of experiments; one testing the inference of the various models on 4-singer mixtures (referred as use-case 1) and the other on 16-singer mixtures (referred as use-case 2). Both our test-cases were performed in an oracle scenario where the fundamental frequency of each of the sources was pre-computed using the DIO algorithm [35] prior to model inference. This was a limitation that will be discussed further in Chapter 5.

4.2 Results

Subsection 4.2.1 presents the BSS Eval objective results, Subsection 4.2.2 goes over the PEASS measurement results, finally Subsection 4.2.3 presents the subjective results obtained via the MUSHRA subjective listening test that we have led as part of this work. We then conclude this section by running a comparison analysis from these various measurement approaches and see how they potentially correlate with each other.

C-U-Net D-A refers to the domain-agnostic architecture presented in [6] while *C-*

U-Net D-S L, *C-U-Net D-S G*, *C-U-Net D-S G x2*, and *C-U-Net D-S Enc* refer to our four domain-specific adaptations. Table 2 presents a concise summary of all the models used and assessed in this work.

4.2.1 BSS Eval Objective Metric Results

We first conducted objective measurements between the predicted and true audio sources for all the models mentioned as part of Table 2 using the *mir_eval toolbox*³ [24]. The three resulting measurements - SDR, SIR, and SAR [1] - describe respectively the overall quality of the separation, the level of interference with other sources, and lastly the amount of artifact added by the separation algorithm itself. The metrics are computed for each of the SATB singing groups on both our test-sets' predictions, that is, for the test set involving exactly one singer per part and the other involving exactly four singers per part, respectively.

Discussion

Use-Case 1:

The upper portions of Tables 3, 4, and 5 portray the mean \pm std SDR, SIR, and SAR results for our first use-case on all the SATB parts as well as the average, for all five models mentioned in previous sections. We observed that our four domain-specific adaptations (denoted under the dash line), called attention to a significant score gap between domain-agnostic and domain-specific models, with an average increase of about 1.32dB SDR, 1.88dB SIR, and 0.69dB SAR between the two different approaches, with our *Global* adaptation - *C-U-Net D-S G* - performing best across all four parts. These improvements underline an overall better quality of the predicted sources (SDR), a decline in interference between the various predictions (SIR), as well as a slight decrease in algorithmic artifacts (SAR). Our domain-specific architecture hence demonstrates a better ability to cope with the correlated nature of the various SATB sources and seems to predict an appropriate spectral mask for each of them. A reason for the increase of the SAR seeming less drastic in contrast to the

³*mir_eval*: A Transparent Implement of Common MIR Metrics:
http://craffel.github.io/mir_eval/#module-mir_eval.io

two other metrics may be the fact that our approach doesn't impact the nature of the main U-Net architecture, the artifacts produced by the algorithm itself remain thus fairly consistent across the two approaches.

We also observed that our proposed adaptations returned the lowest SDR, SIR, and SAR performances for the Bass part, specifically. This could be due to the fact that the Bass group, among all SATB groups, shares the highest number of harmonics with its other source counterparts, therefore this makes the isolation process for this part particularly challenging in comparison to its homologous parts.

Lastly, we also noted that the mean SDR substantially dropped for the Tenor singing group across nearly all domain-agnostic models, reaching a negative result with the *C-U-Net D-A* architecture (-1.25 dB SDR). We speculated that the reason behind such decline could be directly related to the close nature of the F0 contours for both Alto and Tenor singing groups, making it harder for domain-agnostic architecture to distinguish between the two sources. This limitation brought yet another justification for the conditioning approach we have presented in this work.

Use-Case 2:

The bottom portions of Tables 3, 4, and 5 present the mean \pm std SDR, SIR, and SAR scores on the second use-case test set. We observed that the introduction of more complex mixtures involving a higher number of singers as well as unison singing not only decreased the performance of our proposed models with an average SDR barely surpassing U-Net's for our *C-U-Net D-S G* model and levelling it out for the *C-U-Net D-S L* model, but also increased the performance of the domain-agnostic models by an average of 0.78dB SDR and 1.31dB SIR. We justify this decrease in performance by the fact that the mean of the various pitches present in a singing group is not necessarily representative of the true underlying pitch contour of the group of singers, or unison, that the model is trying to isolate. Since domain-agnostic models, such as the plain U-Net, don't hold this assumption, these architectures are less prone to errors when exposed to this type of mixture setting ⁴.

⁴Audio examples showcasing how the inference of our proposed models compare against other state-of-the-art architectures are available online. On the same page is also included a link

Model	Test Use-Case 1 - SDR (dB)				
	Soprano	Alto	Tenor	Bass	Avg.
<i>Wave-U-Net</i>	2.03±2.2	4.59±2.7	0.92±2.9	2.72±2.5	2.56±2.3
<i>U-Net</i>	3.78±2.1	5.15±3.7	2.29±2.7	3.22±1.5	3.61±2.5
<i>C-U-Net D-A</i>	3.57±2.0	2.05±2.1	-1.25±2.6	1.96±2.2	1.58±2.2
<i>Open-Unmix</i>	5.61±2.1	5.70±2.3	1.60±1.7	3.66±2.2	4.14±2.1

<i>C-U-Net D-S L</i>	3.70±1.3	6.99±1.9	3.82±1.6	3.74±1.7	4.56±1.6
<i>C-U-Net D-S G</i>	5.76±1.2	7.67±1.5	5.39±1.4	4.07±1.8	5.73±1.5
<i>C-U-Net D-S G x2</i>	3.46±1.4	5.30±1.6	1.81±1.7	1.56±1.5	3.03±1.6
<i>C-U-Net D-S Enc</i>	3.05±1.4	5.97±2.1	3.35±1.9	2.99±1.3	3.84±1.7
Model	Test Use-Case 2 - SDR (dB)				
	Soprano	Alto	Tenor	Bass	Avg.
<i>Wave-U-Net</i>	3.30±1.6	4.73±0.8	2.09±2.0	1.24±1.4	2.84±1.5
<i>U-Net</i>	5.14±1.5	6.63±1.0	4.74±1.7	3.12±1.6	4.91±1.4
<i>C-U-Net D-A</i>	4.61±1.8	2.67±2.7	0.52±2.8	1.98±1.6	2.45±2.2
<i>Open-Unmix</i>	6.67±2.1	6.49±1.3	2.70±1.6	3.49±2.0	4.83±1.7

<i>C-U-Net D-S L</i>	4.34±0.9	7.06±1.2	4.77±1.6	3.48±1.5	4.91±1.3
<i>C-U-Net D-S G</i>	5.34±1.2	6.44±1.4	4.93±1.5	3.18±1.1	4.97±1.3
<i>C-U-Net D-S G x2</i>	4.58±1.4	5.51±1.1	3.45±2.1	2.62±1.2	4.04±1.4
<i>C-U-Net D-S Enc</i>	4.53±1.5	6.57±1.3	4.65±1.6	2.98±1.5	4.68±1.5

Table 3: SDR (signal-to-distortion) results mean±std on the four SATB parts and their overall average for the four domain-agnostic architectures as well as for our four proposed domain-specific models. The top table depicts the results obtained from the first use-case test set while the bottom ones are from the second use-case test set.

Model	Test Use-Case 1 - SIR (dB)				
	Soprano	Alto	Tenor	Bass	Avg.
<i>Wave-U-Net</i>	5.99±2.4	9.19±2.9	4.62±2.1	8.49±3.5	7.07±2.7
<i>U-Net</i>	10.28±2.4	10.77±4.1	6.70±3.2	9.45±2.0	9.30±2.9
<i>C-U-Net D-A</i>	10.09±2.6	7.81±1.6	3.32±2.2	7.61±2.4	7.21±2.4
<i>Open-Unmix</i>	12.36±2.7	13.19±2.9	6.43±2.0	11.41±2.6	10.85±2.6

<i>C-U-Net D-S L</i>	9.71±1.7	12.37±1.5	9.89±2.2	9.71±1.7	10.42±1.8
<i>C-U-Net D-S G</i>	12.72±1.8	14.04±1.5	11.79±2.1	9.78±2.1	12.08±1.7
<i>C-U-Net D-S G x2</i>	10.03±2.5	11.01±1.1	8.22±1.8	7.60±2.1	9.21±1.9
<i>C-U-Net D-S Enc</i>	9.41±1.9	11.95±1.5	9.86±1.8	9.74±2.1	10.24±1.8
Model	Test Use-Case 2 - SIR (dB)				
	Soprano	Alto	Tenor	Bass	Avg.
<i>Wave-U-Net</i>	8.13±2.1	10.02±0.9	6.80±2.2	7.45±2.0	8.10±1.8
<i>U-Net</i>	12.41±1.8	13.11±1.2	10.26±1.1	8.50±2.3	11.07±1.6
<i>C-U-Net D-A</i>	11.99±1.8	9.08±2.8	5.65±3.1	7.60±2.0	8.58±2.4
<i>Open-Unmix</i>	14.71±2.8	14.40±1.5	7.95±2.4	10.67±1.8	11.93±2.1

<i>C-U-Net D-S L</i>	10.32±1.1	13.06±1.7	10.77±1.5	8.89±2.2	10.76±1.6
<i>C-U-Net D-S G</i>	12.08±1.5	13.50±2.5	12.05±1.3	8.91±2.1	11.63±1.8
<i>C-U-Net D-S G x2</i>	10.86±1.7	11.22±2.3	10.20±2.2	8.30±2.6	10.15±2.2
<i>C-U-Net D-S Enc</i>	11.15±1.6	13.43±2.0	11.62±1.3	9.19±2.7	11.28±1.9

Table 4: SIR (signal-to-interference) results mean±std on the four SATB parts as well as their overall average for the four domain-agnostic architectures as well as for our four proposed domain-specific models. The top table depicts the results obtained from the first use-case test set while the bottom ones are from the second use-case test set.

Model	Test Use-Case 1 - SAR (dB)				
	Soprano	Alto	Tenor	Bass	Avg.
<i>Wave-U-Net</i>	5.36±1.7	7.11±2.4	4.79±1.4	4.89±1.4	5.50±1.7
<i>U-Net</i>	5.35±1.8	7.13±3.0	5.32±1.8	4.94±1.1	5.69±1.9
<i>C-U-Net D-A</i>	5.19±1.6	4.41±2.8	2.65±1.2	4.12±2.0	4.09±1.9
<i>Open-Unmix</i>	7.00±1.8	6.84±2.0	4.43±1.2	4.83±1.9	5.75±1.7

<i>C-U-Net D-S L</i>	5.44±1.0	8.75±2.0	5.58±1.3	5.51±1.7	6.32±1.5
<i>C-U-Net D-S G</i>	7.02±1.1	9.02±1.6	6.86±1.5	5.93±1.6	7.21±1.4
<i>C-U-Net D-S G x2</i>	5.08±0.9	7.02±1.7	3.65±1.7	3.58±1.1	4.83±1.4
<i>C-U-Net D-S Enc</i>	4.74±1.0	7.55±2.2	4.94±1.9	4.54±0.9	5.43±1.5
Model	Test Use-Case 2 - SAR (dB)				
	Soprano	Alto	Tenor	Bass	Avg.
<i>Wave-U-Net</i>	5.75±1.0	6.73±1.0	4.79±1.5	3.23±0.9	5.13±1.1
<i>U-Net</i>	6.31±1.4	7.97±1.0	6.59±1.8	5.27±1.1	6.54±1.3
<i>C-U-Net D-A</i>	5.77±1.7	4.60±2.9	3.39±1.8	4.15±1.1	4.48±1.9
<i>Open-Unmix</i>	7.60±1.8	7.43±1.3	5.01±1.1	4.80±1.8	6.21±1.5

<i>C-U-Net D-S L</i>	6.02±0.9	8.59±1.2	6.45±1.7	5.50±1.1	6.66±1.2
<i>C-U-Net D-S G</i>	6.68±1.2	7.70±1.3	6.17±1.6	5.17±0.8	6.43±1.2
<i>C-U-Net D-S G x2</i>	6.12±1.1	7.45±1.4	4.97±2.0	4.79±0.5	5.83±1.3
<i>C-U-Net D-S Enc</i>	5.95±1.4	7.84±1.2	6.04±1.7	4.82±1.0	6.16±1.3

Table 5: SAR (signal-to-artifacts) results mean±std on the four SATB parts as well as their overall average for the four domain-agnostic architectures as well as for our four proposed domain-specific models. The top table depicts the results obtained from the first use-case test set while the bottom ones are from the second use-case test set.

4.2.2 PEASS - Perceptually-Motivated Objective Score Results

In addition to the purely objective metrics provided by the BSS Eval toolkit, the perceptually-motivated objective metrics - namely OPS (Overall Perceptual Score), TPS (Target-related Perceptual Score), IPS (Interference-related Perceptual Score), APS (Artifact-related Perceptual Score) - offered as part of the PEASS toolkit, were also used in order to assess our experiment. This evaluation framework, similarly to the *mir_eval toolbox*, is publicly available and distributed online as a MATLAB software ⁵. The two same test sets that were used in Subsection 4.2.1 were also evaluated in this context. The process behind the PEASS evaluation (described in detail in Subsection 2.3.3) entails a first step which consists in computing a set of auditory-motivated features derived from a model of auditory perception (PEMO-Q/PSM) [28], features which are then fed into a neural network trained with subjective data, which then outputs a set of objective measures going from 0 (poor perceptual score) up to 100.

Model	PEASS Scores			
	OPS	TPS	APS	IPS
<i>Wave-U-Net</i>	27.50 ±6.00	51.14±14.24	0.16±0.16	84.46 ±2.62
<i>U-Net</i>	19.54±3.17	48.87±12.68	0.53±0.51	82.07±2.39
<i>C-U-Net D-A</i>	22.69±5.50	4.65±3.70	1.71±2.18	79.91±2.79
<i>Open-Unmix</i>	22.58±4.05	52.42 ±11.93	0.42±0.41	83.52±2.13

<i>C-U-Net D-S L</i>	17.67±2.66	11.07±6.68	5.91 ±4.86	80.23±2.21
<i>C-U-Net D-S G</i>	16.23±2.64	11.00±5.55	5.67±4.42	81.21±1.80
<i>C-U-Net D-S G x2</i>	18.70±3.05	8.53±5.38	4.47±3.87	81.34±1.75
<i>C-U-Net D-S Enc</i>	17.80±3.08	8.92±5.53	4.67±4.44	80.96±1.98

Table 6: Overall TPS, IPS, OPS, and APS means±std across all parts and use-cases.

to the models that were trained as part of this experiment: <https://darius522.github.io/satb-source-separation-results/>

⁵The PEASS Toolkit Perceptual Evaluation methods for Audio Source Separation: <http://bass-db.gforge.inria.fr/peass/>

Figure 16: Perceptually motivated objective metrics - TPS, IPS, APS, and OPS - for the **soprano** part for our first use-case (upper figure) and second use-case (lower figure).

Figure 17: Perceptually motivated objective metrics - TPS, IPS, APS, and OPS - for the **alto** part for our first use-case (upper figure) and second use-case (lower figure).

Figure 18: Perceptually motivated objective metrics - TPS, IPS, APS, and OPS - for the **tenor** part for our first use-case (upper figure) and second use-case (lower figure).

Figure 19: Perceptually motivated objective metrics - TPS, IPS, APS, and OPS - for the **bass** part for our first use-case (upper figure) and second use-case (lower figure).

Discussion

Based on the various scores provided in Figs. 16 to 19 as well as in Table 6, we observed that the various interference scores (IPS) returned were not only substantially high for all models but also fairly consistent across all models ($\mu_{IPS} = 81.72$, $\sigma_{IPS} = 0.02$). For fairness in our comparisons, we gave the standard deviation as a fraction of its mean rather than absolute values. We speculate that the reason for such high IPS across nearly all models is the existence of a high correlation between the sources and thus the impact of interfering sources on the predictions are considered perceptually minor.

We also noticed that the preservation of the original target source in the prediction (TPS) is not necessarily a good indicator in itself of the isolation quality. As an example Wave-U-Net, which is, according to the BSS Eval results, the least proficient model with regard to our task, returns by far the highest overall TPS score ($\mu_{TPS} = 51.14$) for both use-cases against an overall average of $\mu_{TPS} = 20.78$ across all other models. This could be explained by the fact that while adding a substantial amount of artifacts to the predictions ($\mu_{APS} = 0.17$ overall), the architecture does not take much off the original target source, which results in a fairly low APS while still maintaining a high TPS. We hypothesize that one explanation for the low TPS returned by our models could be the fact that the introduction of an external control mechanism makes the system more robust in coping with microphone bleed. As our test-set sources haven't been recorded in an isolated space, they do contain some bleed that happens to be substantially reduced by our model during inference, therefore the TPS gets understandably penalized by this reduction.

It could be inferred from Table 6 that while the IPS and OPS seemed to remain static across the various models ($\sigma_{IPS} = 0.02$, $\sigma_{OPS} = 0.13$), the two best discriminators were seemingly the APS followed by the TPS metrics since both displayed signs of important fluctuations across the various models ($\sigma_{APS} = 0.46$, $\sigma_{TPS} = 0.22$). This observation, paired with previous studies which concluded that the APS metric had the strongest correlation with the subjective judgements of artifacts and distortions [29], showed that our set of domain-specific models gave more promising

results than the domain-agnostic counterpart models.

As a final observation, we also noted that the vast majority of the metrics described in this section (with the exception of the APS metric) did not properly reflect well with the preliminary conclusions that we have drawn from our BSS Eval objective results, with the most proficient architectures being reported as Open-Unmix followed closely by Wave-U-Net and U-Net, all outlining high TPS and IPS values, despite their APS being minor, and our models being reported overall as the least proficient ones, mainly because of their low TPS.

The various observations made in this section justified the need for an additional, subjective, testing procedure, in order to assess our work in a fair manner.

4.2.3 Subjective Listening Test Score Results

Lastly, on top of the the PEASS and BSS Eval objective evaluations described in previous subsections, we opted to assess our approach in the form of a “Multi-Stimulus test with Hidden Reference and Anchor” (MUSHRA) [30] listening assessment. Our test implementation was built on top of [26], which provides a framework ⁶ to create browser based listening tests. The test consisted in gathering ratings from subjects by asking them to rate various audio excerpts based on three perceptual criteria: *Source Separation* (SS), which depicts how close to a single voice (for use-case 1) or to a unison (for use-case 2) the audio example sounds, *Content Matching* (CM), referring to how close the predicted source’s content is to the original reference’s content - this could include features such as preservation of words, elocution and articulation, as well as intelligibility. Lastly *Overall Audio Quality* (OQ), which depicts the listener’s overall perceptual impression regarding the quality of the isolated vocal - this could take into account any possible audio impairments that the listeners may deem relevant. Leading this type of subjective test as part of our experiment was not only useful to assess our approach further but it also allowed us to draw a comparative analysis of the various measurement approaches taken in this work (see Subsection 4.2.4).

⁶BeagleJS subjective listening test framework: <https://github.com/HSU-ANT/beaglejs>

Procedure

In order to make the test achievable within reasonable time constraints, we opted to include only 3 of the 8 previously assessed models as part of this test: the original U-Net, its domain-agnostic conditioned counterpart, and our best performing domain-specific model, *C-U-Net D-S G*. We asked the subjects to rate excerpts from these three models based on the three above-mentioned perceptual aspects for the four SATB parts on the two use-cases, for a total of 8 different trials. Fig. 21 shows an example the test interface for one trial; each test item represents a specific model to be assessed based on three perceptual criteria (SS, CM, OQ). In addition to the three model excerpts, a reference working as a *hidden higher anchor* was also included as part of each trial. Ideally, hidden lower and higher anchors would be provided specifically for each perceptual task, however due to the limited time constraints entailed by the nature of this type of listening test, this approach was not feasible in the context of this work.

Participants

The listening test involved a total of 16 participants, all of whom completed the test online. At the end of the test the participants were also asked to assess their level of familiarity with choral music on a 4-point scale, 1 corresponding to very rare to no exposure to the type of music while 4 signifying a fairly frequent exposure. By doing so we were enabled, to a certain extent, to evaluate the level of aptitude and confidence of the subjects towards taking this test. The test subjects' familiarity distribution is given by Fig. 20. We observed that 75% (12) of the test takers responded as being at least slightly familiar with choral music while the remaining 25% (4) were not at all familiar with it.

Figure 20: Test subjects' familiarity distribution with choral music.

Mix	<input type="button" value="Play"/>	<input type="button" value="Stop"/>	
Reference	<input type="button" value="Play"/>	<input type="button" value="Stop"/>	
	<input type="button" value="Play"/>	<input type="button" value="Stop"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Bad <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent
Test Item 1	»»	Source Separation	<input type="range"/>
	»»	Content Matching	<input type="range"/>
	»»	Audio Quality	<input type="range"/>
	<input type="button" value="Play"/>	<input type="button" value="Stop"/>	
Test Item 2	»»	Source Separation	<input type="range"/>
	»»	Content Matching	<input type="range"/>
	»»	Audio Quality	<input type="range"/>
	<input type="button" value="Play"/>	<input type="button" value="Stop"/>	
Test Item 3	»»	Source Separation	<input type="range"/>
	»»	Content Matching	<input type="range"/>
	»»	Audio Quality	<input type="range"/>
	<input type="button" value="Play"/>	<input type="button" value="Stop"/>	
Test Item 5	»»	Source Separation	<input type="range"/>
	»»	Content Matching	<input type="range"/>
	»»	Audio Quality	<input type="range"/>

Figure 21: Interface presented to the test subjects as part of the subjective evaluation of our experiment for one trial (8 in total). Each test item depicts either the hidden reference or an audio excerpt predicted by one of the three models and to be assessed by the subject, given three perceptual criteria.

Figure 22: MUSHRA subjective listening test results for the **soprano** part, targeting three perceptual aspects: **Source Separation Quality (SS)**, **Content Matching (CM)**, **Overall Quality (OQ)**, for our first use-case (upper figure) and second use-case (lower figure).

Figure 23: MUSHRA subjective listening test results for the **alto** part, targeting three perceptual aspects: **Source Separation Quality (SS)**, **Content Matching (CM)**, **Overall Quality (OQ)**, for our first use-case (upper figure) and second use-case (lower figure).

Figure 24: MUSHRA subjective listening test results for the **tenor** part, targeting three perceptual aspects: **Source Separation Quality (SS)**, **Content Matching (CM)**, **Overall Quality (OQ)**, for our first use-case (upper figure) and second use-case (lower figure).

Figure 25: MUSHRA subjective listening test results for the **bass** part, targeting three perceptual aspects: **Source Separation Quality (SS)**, **Content Matching (CM)**, **Overall Quality (OQ)**, for our first use-case (upper figure) and second use-case (lower figure).

Discussion

Figs. 22 to 25 provide the ratings' mean and standard deviation for all three assessed perceptual aspects (SS, CM, OQ). It could be observed that the overall rating levels across the three models followed the same trend as seen in the BSS Eval results, where *C-U-Net D-A* returned the lowest results of the three with an overall average score (all scores combined over all parts and use-cases) of 29.85, followed by U-Net with 49.31, and lastly *C-U-Net D-S G*, which surpassed the first two with 58.67.

The standard deviation remained reasonably static across all parts and use-cases, which showed that all subjects remained fairly consistent in their ratings across the various trials.

Following the same observation made in Subsection 4.2.1, we noted both a decrease in performance for *C-U-Net D-S G* and an increase for U-Net from the first to the second use-case, with an overall score increase of 10.86 for U-Net and a minor score decrease of 2.52 for *C-U-Net D-S G*.

Most ratings assigned to the hidden higher anchor revolved around the "Good" and "Excellent" grades, sometimes barely surpassing the former grade ($\mu_{SS} = 82.48$ for the first use-case). We surmise that one of the reasons behind this could be the fact that the reference recordings used as the higher anchor contained slight bleeds coming from the other parts, which would explain why the SS was the most affected aspect out of the three in the Reference ratings. The fact that the reference ratings happened to be higher for the second use-case counterpart ($\mu_{SS} = 91.59$) upheld this theory, the bleed being probably less perceivable in a unison-type of setting where more singers are involved rather than in a single singer setting.

We noticed a recurring trend among the three aspect ratings across nearly all 8 trials, that is: the OQ aspect ended up being rated the harshest overall ($\mu_{OQ} = 50.93$ for the overall OQ mean score), the CM aspect ended up being rated the most generously ($\mu_{CM} = 62.19$ for the overall CM mean score), while the SS score laid in the middle. This could potentially be explained by the fact that OQ represents the overall perceptual impression aspect and required the subject to take *any* possible

impairments into account while rating the aspect. Furthermore the CM score being high could be explained by the fact that most subjects were not fluent in the language in which the material was performed (i.e Catalan), making them less sensitive to the content and allowing a greater tolerance regarding this aspect, specifically.

As a last observation, it is relevant to note that, following the same trend as observed in Subsection 4.2.1, the isolation performance per part is led by the alto part with $\mu_{overall} = 50.47$ overall (i.e. all aspects and use-cases combined and with reference ratings excluded), followed by the soprano part with $\mu_{overall} = 48.29$, bass and tenor parts yielding the lowest performances with $\mu_{overall} = 42.58$ and $\mu_{overall} = 42.41$, respectively.

4.2.4 Measurement Comparisons

Lastly, we proceeded the same way as in [29] by leading a metric comparison analysis across the BSS Eval and PEASS results in order to assess the performance and relevance of the two measurement approaches against the MUSHRA subjective listening test results.

In [29] the comparison was done through a Spearman correlation on a per-song basis. The experiment consisted in a MUSHRA test similar to the one we have led in this work (Subsection 4.2.3, in which participants were asked to rate 8 test sounds in comparison to a reference sound based on two perceptual aspects - "Interference" and "Audio Quality" - for a total of 16 different trials. The experiment involved a total of 24 participants and resulted in a grand total of 6144 subjective ratings, which allowed the authors to draw correlations across many data points with high p-value.

Since our subjective test didn't involve individual per-song ratings but rather model predictions of parts, one possible approach would have been to compute the correlation between every metrics and subjective tasks on a per model/part-basis, however due to the rather limited size of our rating set, we opted to, instead, compute the error difference measurements between the objective metrics (BSS Eval and PEASS)

Figure 26: Bee swarm plots (with boxplots underlaid) of the errors rates (error difference) between the PEASS/BSS Eval metrics and the MUSHRA subjective ratings, on a per-model and per-part basis.

and the MUSHRA subjective ratings. As previously mentioned, because of the time constraints involved with this test, we deemed appropriate to only include some of the most relevant models as part of the test, that is U-Net, *C-U-Net D-A*, and *C-U-Net D-S G*. With this in mind, the comparison analysis drawn from the data was less robust compared to the correlation drawn in [29], which involved eight models in total.

Prior to computing the error rates, all the measurements have been rescaled from 0 to 100, ratings with the lowest, respectively highest, value corresponding to 0, resp. 100. This allowed us to compare each of the measurement approaches on a common scale. In the case of the MUSHRA results, it entailed removing the hidden reference

ratings from the data prior to the re-scaling process.

Fig. 26 provides the various error rates between the subjective ratings and the objective metrics, for the three subjective aspects assessed in the MUSHRA test that we have led, namely *Source Separation*, *Content Matching*, and *Overall Quality*. Each data point represents the error rate of a prediction for one of the three assessed models against the mean of the subjective ratings (16 in total) for the corresponding part and model. The red diamond indicates the mean error rate for each metric while the inner vertical line indicates the median value of the distribution for a given metric.

For both *Source Separation* as well as *Overall Quality* aspects, we observed that the lowest error difference values across all metrics were returned by the BSS Eval measurements, with $\mu_{SAR} = 15.74$ for SS and $\mu_{SAR} = 17.67$ for OQ (denoted in the red boxplots). Furthermore we noticed that the PEASS counterpart of SAR, namely APS, was also returning among the lowest means ($\mu_{APS} = 23.62$) for the OQ aspect. These observations are in accordance with previous studies [37, 38] on the subject that found strong associations between SAR and APS with the perception of sound quality.

Additionally, we noted that the TPS metric, which was described as the most discriminative one among all the PEASS results but was reporting poor scores for the domain-specific models, returned some of the highest error values for all three aspects, making it seemingly a weak metric for performance evaluation towards our task.

It was important to note that even though the IPS was returning a fairly low error value for each of the three aspects (e.g. being the top metric for "CM"), it was previously pointed out that the IPS was reporting the best performance for the least efficient of our assessed models (i.e. Wave-U-Net), which was not included as part of the MUSHRA test.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

5.1 Objectives and Contributions

With very little previous work done on this front [39, 33], we hope to have brought significant contributions to a relatively unexplored subfield of audio source separation. In this work, we have presented the task of musical source separation applied to SATB choir recordings; we have built on top of existing Deep Neural Network (DNN) models in order to successfully separate SATB mono recordings into each of their respective singing groups; Soprano, Alto, Tenor, and Bass. We first described and investigated some of the state-of-the-art DNN architectures used for audio source separation tasks, such as the U-Net [4] architecture and its waveform-based adaptation, Wave-U-Net [5], architectures that we referred to in this work as "domain-agnostic" as they don't take into account any domain-knowledge that the source may convey. We then proposed an adaptation of the conditioned U-Net model described in [6], which includes a control mechanism conditioned to the F0 input sources, resulting in four different architectural variants, each embedding and injecting the external input data in various ways.

For training and testing, the Choral Singing Dataset [32] as well as a proprietary dataset was used. By bringing a considerable effort into collecting, consolidating and cleaning these two datasets for this task specifically, we were able to efficiently train

and test all the models involved in this experiment and obtain satisfying comparative results. By means of various different evaluation methods and given two different use-cases - 4-singers mixtures and 16-singers mixtures - we were able to show that taking advantage of domain-knowledge during the training process improved the separation performance on both of our proposed use-cases.

Through this work, we hope that researchers will be able to benefit from the various architectures that we have proposed ¹ for their own work, not only within the scope of choral music but also towards tasks involving other sources as well, such as regular speaker mixtures or mixes involving common musical sources. Additionally, we hope that through the comprehensive metric comparison analysis that we have led, researchers will be able to get more insights on the application and significance of these types of measurements (BSS Eval, PEASS, MUSHRA) regarding certain tasks, such as ours, where the sources involved happened to be highly correlated.

5.2 Future Work

In Section 4.2 we have described the limitations entailed by our approach, the first and most prominent one being the fact that the oracle F0 is currently needed and used as external control input data to the network. With this in mind we plan on addressing this constraint by combining the task of multi-pitch tracking [40] to our work in order to make the F0 contour extraction step an integral part of our pipeline. Furthermore the matter of unison was hardly addressed in this work, consequently we plan on combining some of the research that have been led at the MTG on that front and propose a more comprehensive framework capable of not only segregating between the various SATB singing groups but between the unison voices as well.

Furthermore we saw that the improvement brought by our models were not as noticeable on mixtures involving a complex musical setting, such as depicted by our second use-case (i.e. multiple singers per singing group). We hypothesized that the reason for this was the way the F0 contours of unisons were computed (i.e. by taking the mean of the various F0s). With this in mind, we plan taking into consideration

¹<https://github.com/darius522/cunet.git>

other statistical methods such as the variance, in order to push for a more accurate F0 representation for unison.

Lastly, we plan on exploring applications of the SATB separation, including but not limited to remixing the separated voices for increased emphasis, transposition of the choir recording and transcription of the individual parts in the choir.

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